

TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHER EDUCATORS IN RELATION TO GENDER AND WORK MOTIVATION

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ABSTRACT

The investigation was carried out to study the teaching effectiveness of teacher educators in relation to gender and work motivation. Descriptive survey method was used to carry the investigation. Incidental sampling technique was used to select the representative sample of 269 teacher educators from 27 B.Ed. colleges of Himachal Pradesh. Data were collected with the help of Teaching Effectiveness Scale by Dr. Umme Kulsum and Work Motivation Questionnaire by K.G. Aggarwal. Descriptive statistics and Analysis of variance were used to analyze the data. The results of the study indicated that male and female teacher educators do not differ significantly with respect to their teaching effectiveness. There exists no significant difference in the teaching effectiveness of teacher educators with respect to different level of work motivation. Gender and work motivation interact significantly with respect to their teaching experience. At the end of the paper, implications of the study have been discussed.

Keywords: Teaching Effectiveness, Gender, Work Motivation.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching effectiveness refers to both the quality of teaching and the capability of teachers. It requires teachers to continually enhance practice by adopting an evaluative mind-set. Teaching effectiveness is informed by growth-focused evaluations of teaching practice, indicators of learning and wellbeing, and is facilitated by a positive school culture. An educational culture that encourages and supports teachers with their continuous growth and development contributes to improving the standards of teaching and outcomes for learners. Teaching effectiveness majorly concerns with the relationship between the dispositions of teachers, teaching acts, classroom environment, and their effect on the learning of students. It depends on the emotional (kind, warm, compassionate), cognitive (using innovative teaching techniques, mastery of subject), and behavioural competence (patience, punctual, attentive) of a teacher. A teacher with such qualities is termed as an effective teacher. An effective teacher is the link between the educational institution and the student. He/she is able to use the teaching skills to bring out the best in a student thus increasing the school's effectiveness. Furthermore, measuring the teaching effectiveness of a teacher is also very necessary as it helps in improving the quality of teaching. The periodic feedback also helps in recognizing the gaps in teaching and in formulation of remedial plans. There are several internal and external factors that determine the effectiveness of teaching. To summarize, it may be said that teaching effectiveness is an area of research that deals with the professional and personal competence of a teacher. There are various factors which help to enhance the teaching effectiveness of teacher educators. Work motivation is one of them. Work motivation is concerned with factors that energize, channel, sustain and amplify work performance toward organizational goals. Gaps between motivation and performance exist whenever people avoid starting something new, resist doing something familiar, stop doing something important and switch their attention to a less valued task, or refuse to “work smart” on a new challenge and instead use old, familiar but inadequate solutions to solve a new problem. Motivation as a process starts with a physiological or psychological deficiency or need that

activates behaviour or a drive that is aimed at a goal or incentive. Thus motivation consists of three interacting and interdependent elements: need, drives and incentives. Work motivation plays a vital role in the development of organizations, as it increases employee productivity and effectiveness. **Bala and Bashir (2016)** revealed that negative significant relationship existed between teaching effectiveness of secondary school teachers with work motivation. Lata and **Sharma (2016)** found that male and female elementary school teachers differed significantly in their teacher effectiveness. There existed a significant difference in teacher effectiveness of elementary school teachers with respect to their level of professional commitment. There was no significant interactional effect of gender and level of professional commitment on teacher effectiveness of elementary school teacher. **Lata and Sharma (2017)** in their study revealed that teacher effectiveness and work motivation of elementary school teachers correlate positively and significantly to each other irrespective of their level of job satisfaction. Work motivation and job satisfaction do not contribute significantly to the teacher effectiveness of elementary school teachers.

The study also found no significant correlation between teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction of elementary school teachers irrespective of their level of work motivation. **Hadiya (2019)** found the positive and significant correlation between teacher effectiveness and work motivation which means teachers with high work motivation exhibited a higher level of teacher effectiveness as compared to those having lower work motivation. **Sharma (2021)** revealed that there was no significant relationship between work motivation and the effectiveness of the teaching staff and professors of colleges. Further, it was found that there was no significant relationship between work motivation and teacher's effectiveness of private college professors and teachings staff. **Vo, Thuy-Thi-Diem et.al (2022)** showed that autonomy and social relatedness positively impacted work motivation, while competence negatively influenced work motivation. Moreover, the individual-level associations were moderated by the country-level religious affiliation, political participation, humane orientation, and in-group collectivism. **Roche & Pushpa (2023)** in their study revealed that majority of the secondary school teachers possessed above average level of work motivation and high level of attitude towards teaching profession. There was a positive correlation found between work motivation and the attitude towards teaching profession of secondary school teachers. The findings revealed that positive attitude towards teaching profession enhances work motivation and vice-versa.

It has been observed on the basis of the thorough review of the literature that very few studies are on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators. Hence, it was decided to see the impact of gender and work motivation on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the gender-wise difference among teacher educators with respect to their teaching effectiveness.
2. To study the difference in teaching effectiveness of teacher educators with respect to their level of work motivation.
3. To study the interaction between gender and work motivation with respect to teaching effectiveness of teacher educators.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There will be no significant gender-wise difference among teacher educators with respect to their teaching effectiveness.
2. There will be no significant difference in teaching effectiveness of teacher educators with respect to their level of work motivation.
3. Gender and work motivation will not interact significantly with respect to teaching effectiveness of teacher educators.

METHODOLOGY

For conducting the present investigation, survey technique under descriptive method of research was used.

SAMPLING

In the present investigation, a representative sample of 269 teacher educators was selected from 27 B.Ed. colleges of Bilaspur, Kangra, Mandi, Kullu and Shimla districts of Himachal Pradesh by applying incidental sampling technique.

RESEARCH TOOLS USED

In the present study, following research tools were used to collect the data:

1. Teacher Effectiveness scale by Umme Kulsum (2011).
2. Work Motivation Questionnaire by K.G. Agarwal (2012).

ANALYSIS OF DATA

The data were analyzed with the help of descriptive statistics and analysis of variance (Two-Way). Detail description of the analysis is given below:

1. In order to study the main and Interactional effect of gender and level of work motivation on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators, Analysis of Variance (2 x 3 factor design) involving two levels of gender i.e. male and female and three levels of work motivation i.e. high, moderate and low, was applied on mean scores of teaching effectiveness. The selected teacher educators were classified by employing the procedure of $M \pm 1SD$. The mean teaching effectiveness scores of teacher educators with respect to gender and level of work motivation are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

MEANS AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS OF TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS SCORES OF TEACHER EDUCATORS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER AND WORK MOTIVATION

Sr. No.	Levels of Work Motivation Gender	Mean Teaching Effectiveness scores				
		High Level	Moderate Level	Low Level	Total	
1	Male (63)	Mean	480.46	507.53	503.40	501.29
		S.D.	86.198	32.697	39.814	49.573
		N	13	40	10	63
2	Female (206)	Mean	537.39	490.61	472.00	493.63
		S.D.	32.204	65.697	73.613	66.147
		N	23	152	31	206
3	Total (269)	Mean	516.83	494.14	479.66	494.97
		S.D.	62.995	60.646	67.876	62.67
		N	36	192	41	269

From the mean teaching effectiveness scores of teacher educators with respect to gender and level of work motivation, F- values were calculated. The summary of results is given in Table 2 as follows:

TABLE 2

SUMMARY OF ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE FOR TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHER EDUCATORS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER AND WORKMOTIVATION

Sr. No.	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square (Variance)	F- Ratio
1.	Gender(A)	261.210	1	261.210	0.070 ^{NS}
2.	Work Motivation (B)	7135.892	2	3567.946	0.955 ^{NS}
3.	Gender × Work Motivation(A× B)	41536.024	2	20768.012	5.561**
4.	ErrorVariance	982235.183	263	3734.735	
5.	Totalsum of squares	1052620.699	268		

NS-Not Significant

****Significant at 0.01 Level of Significance**

MAIN EFFECTS

(A) GENDER (A)

The calculated value of F- Ratio for the main effect of gender on Teaching Effectiveness of teacher educators, for degree of freedom 1 and 263, came out to be 0.070, which is less than the table value (3.87) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence hypothesis no.1 that “There will be no significant gender-wise difference among teacher educators with respect to their teaching effectiveness” was accepted.

Therefore, it may be interpreted that there was no significant difference in teaching effectiveness of male and female teacher educators. The male teacher educators had shown mean score of 501.29 and female teacher educators had shown mean teaching effectiveness score of 493.03. However, on the basis of mean scores, it can be concluded that male teacher educators have reflected somewhat higher teaching effectiveness as compared to female teacher educators. The mean teaching effectiveness scores of male and female teacher educators can also be shown from figure 1 as follows:

FIGURE 1

MEAN TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS SCORES OF TEACHER EDUCATORS WITH RESPECT TO THEIR GENDER

(B) WORK MOTIVATION (B)

The calculated value of 'F- Ratio' for the main effect of work motivation on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators, for degree of freedom 2 and 263, came out to be 0.955 which is below the table value (3.03) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the hypothesis no. 2 that, "There will be no significant difference in teaching effectiveness of teacher educators with respect to their level of work motivation" was accepted. So, it was inferred that teacher educators possessing different level of work motivation do not differ significantly from each other with regard to their teaching effectiveness.

From Table 1, it can be seen that the mean value of teaching effectiveness scores obtained by the high, moderate and low work motivated teacher educators have been found as 516.83, 494.14 and 479.66 respectively. Although, teacher educators with high work motivation (516.83) possessed higher teaching effectiveness as compared to moderate (494.14) and low work motivated (479.66) teacher educators.

Figure 2 shows the pictorial representation of mean teaching effectiveness scores of teacher educators with respect to level of work motivation.

FIGURE 2

MEAN TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS SCORES OF TEACHER EDUCATORS WITH RESPECT TO LEVEL OF WORK MOTIVATION

INTERACTIONAL EFFECT(A X B)

It is evident from the table that the obtained value of 'F-Ratio' for interactional effect of gender and work motivation on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators, for degree of freedom 2 and 263, came out to be 5.561, which is greater than the table value (4.68) at 0.01 level of significance. Hence hypothesis no. 3 that, "Gender and work motivation will not interact significantly with respect to teaching effectiveness of teacher educators," was not accepted. This showed that gender and level of work motivation taken together influenced teaching effectiveness of teacher educators significantly.

The significant interactional effect of gender and work motivation on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators is shown in figure 3 as follows:

FIGURE 3

SIGNIFICANT INTERACTIONAL EFFECT OF GENDER AND WORK MOTIVATION WITH RESPECT TO TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS

CONCLUSION

1. The results of study revealed that the calculated value of F- Ratio for the main effect of gender on Teaching Effectiveness of teacher educators, for degree of freedom 1 and 263, came out to be 0.070, which is less than the table value (3.87) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it may be interpreted that there was no significant difference in teaching effectiveness of male and female teacher educators. The male teacher educators had shown mean score of 501.29 and female teacher educators had shown mean teaching effectiveness score of 493.03. However, on the basis of mean scores, it can be concluded that male teacher educators have reflected somewhat higher teaching effectiveness as compared to female teacher educators.
2. The calculated value of 'F- Ratio' for the main effect of work motivation on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators, for degree of freedom 2 and 263, came out to be 0.955 which is below the table value (3.03) at 0.05 level of significance. So, it was inferred that teacher educators possessing different level of work motivation do not differ significantly from each other with regard to their teaching effectiveness. Further, it can be seen that the mean value of teaching effectiveness scores obtained by the high, moderate and low work motivated teacher educators have been found as 516.83, 494.14 and 479.66 respectively. Although, teacher educators with high work motivation (516.83) possessed higher teaching effectiveness as compared to moderate (494.14) and low work motivated (479.66) teacher educators.
3. The obtained value of 'F-Ratio' for interactional effect of gender and work motivation on teaching effectiveness of teacher educators, for degree of freedom 2 and 263, came out to be 5.561, which is greater than the table value (4.68) at 0.01 level of significance. This showed that gender and level of work motivation taken together influenced teaching effectiveness of teacher educators significantly.

IMPLICATIONS

The present investigation was conducted to study the teaching effectiveness of teacher educators with respect to gender and work motivation. After drawing out the results from the study, it was found that there was no significant difference in teaching effectiveness of male and female teacher educators. However, on the basis of mean scores, it was concluded that male teacher educators have reflected somewhat higher teaching effectiveness as compared to female teacher educators. It is therefore

essential that some efforts should be made by educationist, policy planners and authorities to increase the teaching effectiveness of female teacher educators. It is also observed that teacher educators with high work motivation possessed higher teaching effectiveness as compared to moderate and low work motivated teacher educators. Therefore, it is necessary to identify teacher's drives and needs to motivate them towards their work. Lack of motivation may lead to stress which eventually translate to ineffective teaching and adversely affect pupil's learning. Everybody needs encouragement and everybody needs their work to be recognized. The teacher training institutions should introduce formal programs that encourage peer recognition for a job well done.

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